

Structural Studies on α -Pinene Dimers. I. A Three Dimensional Cage Structure by Phosphoric Acid Dimerization^{a*}

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This investigation deals with the isolation and structure elucidation of a three dimensional cage-like dimer of α -pinene, produced by phosphoric acid. Chemical, infrared, nuclear magnetic resonance, and mass spectral studies are consistent with the proposed structure. A diepoxide of the dimer was also prepared and structural investigations on this derivative are also consistent with the proposed structure. A number of model compounds which simulate the structural features of the dimer and its epoxide were also prepared and characterized. The results of chemical and spectral examination of these compounds support the proposed structure of the dimer.

The dimerization of α -pinene with phosphoric acid has been investigated. Acid catalysed reactions of α -pinene to give isomers, dimers and polymers have been known for a long time¹. Carter² has reported dimerization of α -pinene using 85% phosphoric acid in good yields. He has also studied the action of phosphoric acid on several other terpenes and observed that *d* or 1- α -pinene and *d*-limonene gave dimeric products which are very similar, if not identical. He observed that the dimeric products were probably mixtures of several isomers. α -terpinene was the major product in his isomeric fraction. Ritter³ has also studied the dimerization of α -pinene using the procedure of Carter and studied dehydrogenation of the dimer (apparently considered as a pure product). 2,6,9-Trimethylphenanthrene was identified to be one of the components in the dehydrogenation products.³

Dehn⁴ reported formation of a large number of unidentified products by reaction of α -pinene with phosphoric acid at 200°. Dipentene, camphene, ethyl α -terpinyl ether and α -terpineol were identified by Hirao⁵ in the reaction products from α -pinene and 3.5 *N* alcoholic phosphoric acid. However, when 10 *N* phosphoric acid was used, the products were terpinolene, *p*-cymene and cineole. A patent is available⁶ for conversion of α -pinene into a

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mixture of α -terpinene and dipentene. In another reaction recorded by Klyuev⁷, 3-*p*-mentene, α -terpinene, *p*-cymene and 2,4(8)-*p*-menthadiene and dimer were obtained. He reacted α -pinene with phosphoric acid and activated charcoal in benzene. Thus, though the reaction has been studied by several researchers, and various structures proposed, no structure is available with systematic evidence to support it.

This reaction has been reinvestigated in detail. The fractionation was done by repeated distillation and the details are given in the experimental part. There were at least eleven products in the isomeric fraction containing six major components. Pure components were obtained by preparative gas chromatography and identified to be (in order of appearance): (1) 3-*p*-methene, (2) camphene, (3) α -terpinene, (4) γ -terpinene, (5) *p*-cymene and (6) 2,4(8)-*p*-menthadiene. The other components (at least five) were present in very small amounts and could not be isolated and identified. Gas chromatographic analysis of the dimeric fraction showed 6-8 components. A procedure of stirring α -pinene and 85% phosphoric acid (in molar ratio 1 : 0.9) for 18 hours at 30°-40° was studied first but a number of variations in the process were studied in attempts to reduce the complexity of the reaction mixture.

The reaction was studied more from the qualitative view point rather than the quantitative. Since the distillation is continuous with no sharp changes in temperature between the dimer and trimer fraction, it is not possible to make an accurate estimation of the quantity of dimeric hydrocarbons. The maximum temperature reached in the reaction was dependent on the rate of stirring. This is understandable because the reaction mixture is a two phase system. In one reaction, where very vigorous stirring was employed, the temperature rose to 67°. The flask was then cooled with a water bath to prevent an uncontrollable reaction. The reaction mixture gave products in amounts fairly consistent with those reported earlier. The amount of high boiling residues was slightly higher (ca 7-8%). In other reactions, the amount of phosphoric acid was drastically reduced, the reaction temperature was controlled by external cooling, and the course of the reaction followed by V.P.C. as well as by infrared analysis. There was a considerable increase in the reaction time. Furthermore, the amount of dimeric fraction was somewhat reduced and the amount of mono-terpenes formed was higher. Even though the amount of dimeric fraction was reduced there was virtually no change in the composition of the dimeric fraction. The contents showed the presence of at least 8-10 components of which none is a major product. The quantity of any individual dimer thus corresponds to about 2-3% of the starting material. The following observations have been noted during the dimerization studies: (a) An increase of temperature up to 70° decreases the yield of desired dimer. (b) An increase of reaction time up to 72 hr at room temperature diminishes the yield of desired dimer. (c) A decrease of the concentration of H₃PO₄ to 80% with water does not produce a good yield of desired dimer. (d) The optimum conditions for best yield of the desired dimer with the least number of isomers are to carry out the reaction at room temperature (ca. 28-30°) with constant stirring for 25 hr in a molar ratio of 2.5 (α -pinene) : 0.8 (85% phosphoric acid).

Dimerization of α -pinene with phosphoric acid using tetrahydrofuran as solvent was also investigated. The reaction mixture showed a considerable amount of unchanged

α -pinene and a number of isomeric mono-terpenes. The extent of dimerization was extremely small (as indicated by V.P.C.) and consequently the reaction products were not thoroughly examined. In another experiment α -pinene was converted into its nitrosyl chloride adduct. Attempts were made to react this product with phosphoric acid. However, no products corresponding to the dimers from α -pinene were obtained.

Extensive fractionation was accomplished using a spinning band column (24") (28 theoretical plates) but pure components could not be obtained. The richest fraction contained a single component in amounts up to 70%. More recently, it has been possible to obtain a single component of 95% purity by redistillation of the 70% enriched fraction using a Teflon spinning band column (125 theoretical plates). The 70% fraction was used as such for many of the chemical degradations. Small amounts of a pure component (the first peak in the dimer region in V.P.C. analysis on Carbowax 20M, Versamid 900 and FFAP column, designated as *Dimer A*) for spectral investigations were collected by preparative gas chromatography (Carbowax 20M, 15% on Chromosorb P (40-60 mesh), col. temp. 190°, 15' \times 1/2" column, He 150 ml/min; FFAP 30% on Chromosorb W, 16" \times 1/4" column, col. temp. 210°, inj. and det. temp. 250°, He 100 ml/min).

Chemical Transformations : Chemical degradations by various conventional methods were attempted using the enriched fraction of *Dimer A* as starting material. *Dimer A* was not completely hydrogenated when treated with hydrogen and 5% Pd/C catalyst under one atmospheric pressure, at high pressure (ca. 2000 p.s.i.) nor by diimide reduction⁸. Under identical conditions and in a much shorter time, 2,4(8)-*p*-menthadiene absorbed hydrogen corresponding to two double bonds. The presence of very highly hindered double bonds is indicated as other evidence has shown the molecule to contain two double bonds. For comparison, it has been shown⁹ that steroids having double bonds in the 8,14-position (tetrasubstituted) are resistant to hydrogenation by all known methods. Furthermore, steroids having double bonds in 7,8-positions are likewise unhydrogenable but when shaken with a sufficiently active catalyst (Pd, ether; Pt less effective) with hydrogen, isomerization to the 8,14-position occurs. The IR spectrum of the partially hydrogenated dimer showed the absence of peaks at 1670 cm^{-1} and 820 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond) indicating that only trisubstituted olefinic bonds had undergone hydrogenation. The NMR spectrum of the sample also showed the absence of vinylic protons, substantiating this argument. Ozonolysis of *Dimer A* was also attempted. Both acidic and neutral compounds were isolated. The acidic compound was converted to an ester which could not be purified. The infrared spectrum of the neutral products showed the presence of a strong carbonyl absorption but it could not be purified by repeatedly passing over adsorption alumina. The impure compound gave a 2,4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone, m.p. 90°-95°. Ozonolysis of *Dimer A* under modified conditions^{8b} gave mainly a carbonyl compound which gave a 2 : 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone, m.p. 93°-95°. Its nitrogen content corresponded to a dicarbonyl compound indicating that only the trisubstituted double bond had been oxidised.

Dehydrogenations of *Dimer A* with selenium, sulfur, Pd/C and Rh/C catalysts were attempted. Selenium and sulfur gave extremely complex products. A quantitative determination of the volume of gases evolved, using Pd/C catalyst, was made. Evolution of gases ceased after 2.3-2.5 moles of gases per mole of starting material had been evolved.

Only methane was identified as the organic constituent in the gases. The dehydrogenated products showed absorption at 825 and 1495 cm^{-1} in the infrared spectrum, indicating a 1,4- or 1,2,4- substituted aromatic nucleus in the product. There were at least 10-12 products in the mixture. One of the components was present in slightly higher concentration than the others. A small amount of pure component was obtained by column chromatography over alumina followed by preparative gas chromatography, but the amount was too small to permit its identification. The infrared spectrum showed absorption at 2850-3030 (aliphatic and aromatic C-H), 1495 (aromatic skeletal stretching), 1460 (aliphatic CH_2), 1355-1380 (aliphatic CH_3), 825 cm^{-1} (2 adjacent hydrogens on aromatic nucleus). The NMR spectrum led to the following conclusions: (1) The compound contains only one aromatic nucleus containing 3-4 hydrogens. (2) Only one methyl group is present on the aromatic nucleus. (3) Complete aromatization could not be achieved. Mass spectral analysis gave unusually large peaks at $m/e = 270$ (parent = $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{30}$) and at 255 (parent minus CH_3). The information is, however, not sufficient to establish the structure of the dehydrogenated product. Dehydrogenation with Rh/C catalyst gave similar results. Hydroboration^{8c}-oxidation of the Dimer A did not produce good results. Also, Dimer A did not form complexes with AgNO_3 nor Pd-complex solution.

Oxidations with KMnO_4 and a mixture of KMnO_4 and NaIO_4 ¹⁰ were also attempted. The dimer was readily oxidized. The KMnO_4 reagent however, was too drastic because a considerable amount of the material was oxidized to carbon dioxide (evolution of copious amounts during acidification) and water. Only a small amount (25-30% by weight) of a resinous mixture of acids was formed. This could not be resolved.

Epoxidation of Dimer A with perbenzoic acid gave a solid epoxide. Based upon the quantitative consumption of perbenzoic acid during the epoxidation, elemental analysis, molecular weight data, infrared, NMR and mass spectral analyses, the epoxide was shown to be a diepoxide, thus confirming the presence of two double bonds.

Infrared Studies: The infrared spectrum of Dimer A showed absorptions at 2850-2930 cm^{-1} (aliphatic C-H), 1450 cm^{-1} (C-H deformation in methylene) and 1370-1390 cm^{-1} (gem dimethyl groups), 1670 cm^{-1} and 820 cm^{-1} (trisubstituted double bond). No characteristic bands for tetrasubstituted double bonds are available in the infrared region.¹¹ The ultraviolet spectrum showed the absence of conjugated double bonds but indicated isolated double bonds (λ_{max} (CH_3OH) 195 $m\mu$, $\epsilon = 36,560$). The infrared spectrum of the diepoxide showed bands characteristic of epoxide (790 cm^{-1} and 870 cm^{-1}).

NMR Studies: The nuclear magnetic resonance (NMR) spectrum of Dimer A showed the following characteristic peaks: the peak at 5.45 δ indicated one vinylic proton, in support of previous evidence that one of the double bonds is trisubstituted. The area between 0.75-1.2 δ contained approximately eighteen protons. From the proposed structure of Dimer A (V) it might have been predicted that the allylic methyl protons should absorb at 1.7 δ . However, they were shifted upfield probably due to shielding by the neighbouring olefinic double bonds.¹² An inspection of the molecular model of Dimer A indicates close approach of the allylic methyls to the neighbouring double bonds. The NMR spectrum of the diepoxide showed a peak at 2.7 δ indicative of one epoxide proton, thus supporting

the structure in which one double bond is trisubstituted and one is tetrasubstituted. The area between 1.22-2.1 δ contained approximately thirteen protons. The area between 0.8-1.2 δ contained approximately eighteen protons.

Mass Spectral Studies: Mass spectral analysis of Dimer A gave unusually large peaks at $m/e = 272$ (parent molecular formula = $C_{20}H_{32}$), at $m/e = 257$ (base peak, parent $-CH_3$) and at $m/e = 230$ (parent-42, $\begin{array}{c} CH_3 \\ \diagup \\ C \\ \diagdown \\ CH_3 \end{array}$). There were also relatively large peaks at

$m/e = 242$ (parent $-2CH_3$) and at $m/e = 188$ (parent -84 , $2 \begin{array}{c} CH_3 \\ \diagup \\ C \\ \diagdown \\ CH_3 \end{array}$). A number of peaks of varying intensities (mostly low) were present in the low mass unit region, but no useful information could be obtained from these. The presence of a peak at $m/e = 230$ and absence of a peak at $m/e = 229$ (parent $-C_3H_7 = 43$) indicates that an isopropylidene group is lost and that there is no isopropyl group in the molecule.

Mass spectral data of several monoterpenes have been reported by Rhyage¹³ and Thomas¹⁴. The isopropyl group is invariably severed in the case of monocyclic terpenes. The major peak is always at $m/e =$ parent-43 (C_3H_7) regardless of whether the isopropyl group is situated on the double bond (as in α -terpinene, or γ -terpinene) or on the carbon atom adjacent to a double bond (as in α -phellandrene). Even in *p*-cymene, the major fragment was due to loss of an isopropyl group.

A structure for a dimer of α -pinene (I) was proposed by Mosher, Stuart, and Coder.^{15a} Although this structure was discussed by Wystrach, Barnum, and Garber,^{15b} no reference to its subsequent publication can be found. Mosher, Stuart and Coder^{15a} also studied the reaction of *d*-limonene and terpinolene and observed that the products formed were identical with those obtained from α -pinene. Structure (I) should be susceptible to fragmentation to a much greater extent than that observed in this study.

(I)

There should be a peak at $m/e = 177$ (parent $-C_7H_{11}$). No such peak with any reasonable intensity was observed in this work. It can therefore be concluded that Dimer A of this study does not possess the structure (I) proposed by Mosher, Stuart and Coder.^{15a}

Mass spectral analysis of two hydrocarbons, 3-benzyl-*p*-menthane and 3-*p*-isopropylbenzyl-*p*-menthane (prepared in this study and discussed later) showed extensive fragmentation. Both these compounds have two cyclic units united by a single bridge. All of the

available data indicate that Dimer A cannot be adequately represented by structures which have isopropyl groups nor which possess two ring systems connected by a single bridge.

A mass spectral analysis of the epoxide of 1-methyl-2,4-isopropyl cyclohexane has been done.^{12a, 12b} The fragmentation pattern of this compound is closely related to that of the diepoxide of Dimer A. The epoxide gave a peak at $m/e = 196$ (parent, mol. formula, $C_{13}H_{26}O$); other peaks appeared at $m/e = 281$ (parent $-CH_3$); $m/e = 178$ (parent $-H_2O$ (18)); $m/e = 153$ (base peak, parent $-(COCH_3)(43)$).

Mass spectral analysis of the diepoxide of Dimer A gave a peak at $m/e = 304$ (parent, molecular formula = $C_{20}H_{32}O_2$); other peaks appeared at $m/e = 289$ (parent $-CH_3$); $m/e = 286$ (parent $-H_2O$); $m/e = 271$ (parent $-(CH_3 + H_2O)$); $m/e = 246$ (parent $-COCH_3(43)$); $m/e = 218$ (parent $-2(COCH_3)(86)$); $m/e = 192$ (parent -112).

On the basis of the evidence obtained in this work, a three dimensional cage structure (V) which contains two methyl substituted cyclohexene rings united by two isopropylidene bridges is proposed for Dimer A. The double bonds are highly hindered with one being trisubstituted and the other tetrasubstituted, which could account for the resistance to hydrogenation, dehydrogenation, and many chemical degradations attempted. Complete dehydrogenation of the cyclohexene rings of Dimer A to the aromatic structure would lead to a derivative of 1,1-metacyclophane, a structure which has not been synthesized.

The following scheme is proposed as the mechanism for dimerization of α -pinene to Dimer A.

In the first stage α -pinene is protonated. The α -pinyl carbonium ion then undergoes ring opening of the cyclobutane ring to yield 8-*p*-menthenyl carbonium ion (III). This intermediate can serve as the precursor for the various isomers. The mechanism for formation of the various isomers has been discussed by several workers.¹ In the next step another molecule of α -pinene is attacked on the more highly hindered side by this carbonium ion (III). Ring opening of the cyclobutane ring again occurs. The stereochemistry of this ion (IV) permits the molecule to assume a conformation in which an intramolecular loss of proton can take place. Attack of α -pinene by carbonium ion (III) on the less hindered side could result in a structure similar to (IV); however this product does not appear capable, based upon model studies, of producing a three dimensional cage structure due to conformational limitations. The product obtained by an intramolecular loss of proton from (IV) in the direction to form the more thermodynamically stable tetrasubstituted alkene would have structure (V). A simple proton elimination from (IV) through (IVa), could produce structures analogous to (IVb) and (IVc).

Product (V), which is capable of existing as two enantiomeric pairs of optical isomers (Va and Vb) and (Vc and Vd), meets the structural requirements of Dimer A. In addition, the diepoxide derived from Dimer A possesses properties consistent in every way with those predicted from the structure assigned to Dimer A. It should be pointed out that attack of carbonium ion (III) on the less hindered side of α -pinene, followed by intramolecular loss

Similarly by attack on more highly hindered side:

of a proton, if such could occur in spite of the conformational limitations referred to above, two additional enantiomeric pairs of optical isomers of (V) would result. Also, protonic initiated migration of the trisubstituted double bond of V to the more thermodynamically stable tetrasubstituted position would lead to structures analogous to (Ve, f and g). The various dimers therefore may be double bond isomers of the three dimensional cage structure (V) or of the open chain structure (IVb).

The reaction of 1-limonene with phosphoric acid was also investigated. The dimeric products in both cases had approximately the same number of components and a nearly identical pattern in gas chromatography. One component with retention time corresponding to an α -pinene dimer was collected for spectral investigations. The infrared and NMR spectra indicate that the two compounds are structurally similar. Mass spectral analysis gave almost identical patterns in the two cases which confirms the observation of various workers that identical dimeric products are formed in both cases.

The following mechanism is proposed as the pathway for this dimerization. Since the carbonium ion (III) can be formed from several terpenes including α -pinene, this is the most likely precursor for dimerization.

This mechanism can be considered as an alternate or competitive pathway for the mechanism proposed above and gives products with the same carbon skeleton. As indicated, the proposed three dimensional cage structure is capable of existing as two enantiomeric pairs of optical isomers. However, under the conditions of formation, it is not likely that optical retention would be observed. It is well known that β -pinene¹⁶ leads to a high yield (94%) of reasonably high molecular weight polymer by cationic initiation, while under the same conditions α -pinene leads to a low yield (35%) of low molecular weight polymer and high yield (60%) of a dimer or mixture of dimers. Since carbonium ion (III) is most probably an intermediate in both cases, dimer formation in the case of α -pinene appears to be predominantly a termination step. There appear to be two logical and reasonable explanations for this termination characteristic in the case of α -pinene :

(1) Attack of carbonium ion (III) at a methylene carbon of β -pinene is favoured over an attack at the cyclohexenyl carbon of α -pinene. This is reasonable, but does not explain why attack occurs readily on a second molecule of α -pinene but occurs quite reluctantly on a third or fourth α -pinene molecule. On the other hand, carbonium ion (IVa) is a trialkyl cyclohexene and is therefore considerably more hindered sterically than carbonium ion (III), a dialkyl cyclohexene.

All successive steps in polymer formation would involve identical steric problems. Such

is not the case with β -pinene. (2) The conformationally favoured intramolecular attack of intermediate (IV) to form (V), a termination step, appears to be a factor. Examination of molecular models indicates that formation of (V) or (Va) would be somewhat favoured conformationally over the corresponding dimer (VIa) required from β -pinene.

This factor coupled with the other steric factors mentioned above offers a reasonable explanation for the observations.

Since it was not possible to degrade the dimeric products to known products, a number of reactions were attempted to synthesize C-20 compounds of known structure for comparison. 8-Bromo-*p*-menthene was prepared essentially by the procedure of Bacon.¹⁷ The lithium and the Grignard reagents were prepared by reaction in ether with lithium and magnesium respectively. Condensation of both the reagents with carvomenthone and menthone was attempted. At elevated temperatures the organometallic reagent was destroyed and a small amount of complex high boiling mixture was formed. However, there was no indication of any product that was formed by the condensation of the organometallic reagent with the ketone. The failure of the reaction is probably due to steric hindrance.

Reports concerning the preparation of bimenthyl (VIII) are contradictory.¹⁸ Attempts were made to prepare bimenthyl by reacting 1-menthyl chloride with sodium, using toluene as solvent. No substantial amounts of bimenthyl were formed in this reaction but another hydrocarbon was formed in 15–20% yield. This compound was isolated and identified as 3-benzyl-*p*-menthane (VII) by infrared and mass spectrometry. The infrared spectrum showed peaks at 3030 (aromatic C–H), 2880–2960 (aliphatic C–H), 1600 and 1495 (aromatic), 1450 (aliphatic CH₂), 1365, 1340 (methyl groups in isopropyl group), 735 and 695 cm⁻¹ (mono substituted phenyl). The NMR spectrum of the compound also showed the presence of aromatic hydrogens. However, a singlet for a CH₃ group on aromatic nucleus was missing. These data indicated participation of the methyl group of toluene in formation of the reaction product which was suspected to be 3-benzyl-*p*-menthane. Mass spectral analysis gave major peaks at $m/e = 230$ (parent, C₁₇H₂₆), $m/e = 139$ (*p*-menthyl = C₁₀H₁₉), $m/e = 138$ (*p*-menthyl -H, C₁₀H₁₈), and $m/e = 90$ (benzyl -H, C₇H₆). The fragmentation pattern, elemental analysis and the parent peak at $m/e = 230$ confirm the structure of the product to be 3-benzyl-*p*-menthane (VII).

The reaction was extended to synthesis of C-20 hydrocarbons by substituting *p*-cymene for toluene. Besides a small amount of unidentified products, there was one major product in the reaction mixture. This compound (IX) was isolated in a pure state by fractional distillation. The NMR spectrum of (IX) indicated that (1) an aromatic nucleus was present (7.07 δ) and (2) a methyl group on aromatic nucleus was absent (no peak at 2.43 δ). The presence of an aromatic nucleus was also supported by the infrared spectrum. The mass

Configurations of Proposed α -Pinene Dimers

spectrum gave peaks at $m/e = 272.5$ (parent, $C_{20}H_{32}$), $m/e = 257.5$ (parent, $-CH_3$, $C_{19}H_{29}$), $m/e = 201$, $m/e = 187$, $m/e = 139$ ($C_{10}H_{19}$, *p*-menthyl), $m/e = 138$ ($C_{10}H_{18}$, *p*-menthyl $-H$), $m/e = 134$ ($C_{10}H_{14}$, *p*-cymene), $m/e = 133$ ($C_{10}H_{13}$, *p*-isopropylbenzyl). The last four peaks were very strong and much stronger than the parent peak. This indicated fragmentation

of the parent compound is very facile in mass spectral analysis. On the basis of infrared, NMR, mass spectral and elemental (Vide Experimental) analysis, the product (IX) is assigned the structure, 3-(*p*-isopropylbenzyl)-*p*-menthane (IX).

IX

The proposed mechanism for the formation of 3-benzyl-*p*-menthane from the reaction of toluene, sodium, and 3-chloro-*p*-menthane is presented below. A similar mechanism is also applicable for the parallel reaction of *p*-cymene. The methyl hydrogens in *p*-cymene

are attacked preferentially over the tertiary hydrogen of the isopropyl group. This is probably due to steric interaction of the isopropyl group of 3-chloro-*p*-menthane with the isopropyl group in *p*-cymene.

Reaction of 2-chloro-*p*-menthane, under similar conditions was also attempted. A small amount of high boiling mixture containing 3-4 components was obtained. The infra-red spectrum of the products indicated that there was no aromatic nucleus in the products and that the products were essentially saturated hydrocarbons. The products most probably are bi-2-methyls (IX), the formation of a bi-menthyl being favoured in this case due to reduced steric interactions. This reaction was not investigated further due to low yields of the products.

Opening of the epoxide rings in the diepoxide of Dimer A was attempted by various reagents, such as dilute mineral acids, lithium aluminium hydride, lithium diethylamide, and lithium in ethylamine.¹⁹ The lithium/ethylamine reduction gave a diol which was converted to an acetyl derivative, m.p. 92-4°. Synthesis of epoxide XII as a model compound for the diepoxide of Dimer A was carried out. 1-Methyl-2-hydroxy-2,4-diisopropyl cyclohexane (X) was made by condensing camvomenthone and isopropyl bromide through a Grignard reaction.

The structure of X was confirmed by IR, NMR and elemental analysis. Compound X on dehydration²⁰ by iodine gave XI :

The structure of XI was confirmed by IR, NMR and elemental analysis. Compound XI was treated with perbenzoic acid to give the epoxide XII.

EXPERIMENTAL²¹

Reaction of α -Pinene with Phosphoric Acid: The following general procedure was used for dimerization. α -Pinene (340 g.) was placed in a 3-necked flask equipped with a stirrer, thermometer, addition funnel and a CaCl_2 drying tube. Phosphoric acid (150 ml., 85–87%) was added dropwise over a period of 3 hr. The addition of phosphoric acid was accompanied by an immediate formation of a yellow color. The color deepened to orange and then to brown as the reaction proceeded. The reaction was slightly exothermic, as the reaction temperature rose to 39°–40° and remained at this temperature for about 4 hr. The reaction mixture was then stirred for 18 hr at room temperature (25°–28°), after which the contents were transferred to a separatory funnel. The acid layer (lower) was removed. The organic layer was diluted with an equal amount of pentane (to make the material more mobile), washed twice with 100 ml. fractions of saturated NaHCO_3 solution, and then with water. After drying over Na_2SO_4 , the pentane was removed by distillation at atmospheric pressure. The product was then fractionated by use of a 24" spinning band column under reduced pressure. The results of a typical fractional distillation are shown in Table 1. Fraction 1 showed 8–11 components on V.P.C. analysis. Six of these were major and were collected, using a preparatory chromatograph. Peaks (1–6) in order of appearance have been identified as follows: (1) *p*-3-menthene, (2) camphene, (3) α -terpinene, (4) γ -terpinene, (5) *p*-cymene, and (6) 2,4(8)-*p*-menthadiene.

TABLE 1

Typical fractional distillation results. α -Pinene Dimerization

Fraction number	b.p./mm.	Weight g.	%
1	50°–56°/7.5–2.3	120	35
2	56°–70°/2.3	1	<1
3	80°–90°/0.80	7	2
4	90°–100°/0.4–0.8	110	32
5	100°–110°/0.4	50	14
6	Residue	11	3

The minor components consisted of about 5% at the most (combined) and could not be characterized. This fraction when further treated with H_3PO_4 showed color development but the amount of polymerization was small. Fraction 3 was a mixture of some monoterpene plus dimers. Fraction 4 contained mainly dimers and V.P.C. analysis showed it to be a mixture of 6–8 components. This fraction was further investigated for isolation of pure components. The dimer mixture was again fractionally distilled through the 24" spinning band column, resulting in a fraction containing 75% Dimer A. Redistillation of this fraction through a Teflon spinning band column resulted in 95% pure Dimer A.

Fraction 5 was very viscous and probably contained trimers and/or tetramers also. Because of the high boiling point it was not investigated by use of gas chromatography. The residue solidified to a glassy solid.

Dehydrogenation of Dimer Mixture: Enriched dimeric mixture (75% Dimer A) (3.6 g.) was heated with 4.0 g. of 5% Pd/C catalyst for 20 hr at 310°–330°. Evolution of gases had almost ceased after this time. The infrared spectrum indicated 1,4 or 1,2,4 aromatic substitution by strong absorption at 825 cm⁻¹. Weak absorption at 1495 cm⁻¹ was also noted. The contents were extracted with absolute ethanol and the extract distilled under reduced pressure. Two fractions were collected: (a) b.p. 25°–69°/0.3 mm. and (b) b.p. 69°–75°/0.3 mm. The infrared spectra of both the fractions were nearly superimposable and showed absorption at 825 cm⁻¹. The second fraction contained one component in amounts up to 75%. The major component was collected by preparative gas chromatography.

In another reaction 27.2 g. of dimeric mixture was dehydrogenated with 6 g. of 5% Pd/C catalyst and the contents heated at 310°–330°. A quantitative determination of volume and rate of evolution of gases was made by suitable gas collecting apparatus. Brisk evolution of gases started at 269° and the maximum rate was about 3600 ml./hour. After eight and one-half hours, even at 324°, the rate had dropped to about 35 ml./hour. Heating was stopped, 5 g. of fresh catalyst were added and the contents heated up once more. No significant amount of reaction was noted this time. The total amount of gases evolved amounted to only 2.3 moles/mole of starting material. Methane was identified in the gases. These data indicate that the products are extremely resistant to complete aromatization.

In a third experiment, 4.0 g. of enriched dimer mixture was sealed in a Pyrex tube under nitrogen with 0.4 g. of 10% Pd/C. It was heated in a metal bath at 350° for 20 hr. After this time, the tube was cooled and opened carefully. The escaping gases burned with a blue flame, suggesting the presence of some carbon monoxide. The residue was extracted with ether and the crude product was chromatographed over adsorption alumina (80–200 mesh, 200 g.) (column size: 1.5" × 18"). The adsorbed material was then eluted with *n*-hexane, hexane/benzene and benzene/chloroform in different proportions. About forty fractions, each of about 50 ml., were collected. No fraction yielded a single component. The fractions were mixed and separated in preparative gas chromatography (30% FFAP, 8' col. temp. 210°, inj. and det. temp. 260°). A small fraction was collected which showed aromatic structure in the infrared and NMR spectra.

Hydrogenation of Dimer Mixture: Enriched dimer mixture (3.5 g.) dissolved in 10 ml. *n*-hexane was added to a hydrogenation flask containing 10 ml. *n*-hexane and 0.5 g. 5% Pd/C. Absorption of hydrogen was very rapid for the first 6 hr and continued at a slow rate for the next 36 hr. Based upon hydrogen uptake, the number of double bonds per mole of dimer was indicated to be one. The products of hydrogenation were separated by preparative gas chromatography (30% FFAP, 8' col. temp. 210°, det. and inj. temp. 260°). The pure component was subjected to IR and NMR spectroscopy. The peaks for trisubstituted double bond are absent from the IR spectrum indicating that the trisubstituted double bond has been hydrogenated. The NMR spectrum also showed the absence of vinylic proton. Hydrogenation at 2000 p.s.i. using Pd/C and absolute ethanol as solvent also failed to completely hydrogenate the dimer. Diimide reduction of Dimer A using *p*-toluene-sulfonylhydrazide also failed to completely reduce the double bonds.

Epoxidation of Dimer Mixture : Perbenzoic acid (8.2 g.) dissolved in 200 ml. CHCl_3 was added to 5.4 g. enriched dimer mixture. During addition some heat was developed. It was cooled immediately and kept in the refrigerator for five days. A blank was prepared at the same time without dimer and kept in the refrigerator. After 48, 72 and 96 hr, both the dimer solution and the blank solution were titrated to calculate the amount of consumption of perbenzoic acid. It was found that the consumption of perbenzoic acid was about two moles per mole of dimer. These results suggest the presence of two double bonds in the dimer. After five days the reaction mixture was treated with NaOH solution to remove benzoic acid. The chloroform solution was dried over anhydrous Na_2SO_4 . The thick brown liquid after removal of solvent did not respond to a tetranitromethane test. The crude material, 4 g., was then chromatographed over adsorption alumina (80–200 mesh, 200 g.) (column size, 1.5" \times 18") and eluted with *n*-hexane, pet ether (60°–100°), pet ether/benzene, and benzene/chloroform, in different ratios. At least 100 fractions, each about 50 ml., were collected. The benzene fraction gave a solid compound (1 g.). It was crystallized from dilute ethanol and white flakes were obtained, m.p. 75°. *Anal. Calcd.* for $\text{C}_{20}\text{H}_{32}\text{O}_2$: C, 78.94; H, 10.52. Found : C, 78.85; H, 10.70. Mol. wt., Calcd. : 304. Found (vapour pressure osmometer) : 304.

Ozonolysis of 95% Dimer A gave mainly keto acids and traces of a neutral component. 95% Dimer A was dissolved in CH_2Cl_2 and ozone was passed for 3 hr. After this time, the ozonide mixture was decomposed by 30% H_2O_2 in the cold, and kept overnight at room temperature. Excess H_2O_2 was decomposed by Pd/C. After removal of the aqueous layer, the CH_2Cl_2 layer was evaporated to dryness and treated with ether. The ether solution was then extracted first with NaHCO_3 and then NaOH. Both of these solutions after acidification gave some semi-solid mass.

The crude product gave tests both for $-\text{COOH}$ group and $>\text{CO}$ group. The acids were then converted to the methyl esters by CH_3N_2 . The product was a mixture of 5–6 components. Attempts to purify the mixture by both distillation and column chromatography over Al_2O_3 were not successful. When the above ozonide was decomposed by $(\text{CH}_3)_2\text{S}$ instead of H_2O_2 it gave carbonyl compounds only. This was purified through Girard's reagent. This gave a 2 : 4-dinitrophenyl hydrazone, m.p. 93°–5°. (Calcd. for $\text{C}_{32}\text{H}_{40}\text{O}_{10}\text{N}_8$: N, 13.6%. Found : N, 13.9%).

*Reaction of 3-Chloro-*p*-menthane with Sodium in Toluene* : 3-Chloro-*p*-menthane (8.2 g., 0.047 mole), sodium, 1.08 g. (0.047 mole) and 35 ml. of toluene were heated at reflux for 24 hr after which time no sodium remained. A certain amount of sodium derivative remained as was indicated by the presence of a blue solid. The contents were filtered and distilled under reduced pressure and the following fractions collected : (a) b.p. 25°–55°/0.5 mm. (mainly monoterpenes containing some unreacted 3-chloro-*p*-menthane), (b) b.p. 55°–103°/0.5 mm. (intermediate fractions) and (c) b.p. 103°/0.5 mm. (one component constituted 80% of the mixture). Yield : 12 g. (10%). The major component in fraction (c) was collected by preparative gas chromatography and identified as 3-benzyl-*p*-menthane (VII). The evidence for this structure has already been presented. (Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{26}$: C, 88.62; H, 11.38. Found : C, 88.59; H, 11.40).

Reaction of 3-Chloro-p-menthane with Sodium and p-Cymene: Sodium (2.3 g., 0.1 mole) was granulated by heating in 100 ml. of *p*-cymene. 3-Chloro-*p*-menthane¹⁸ (b.p. 77°–9/8.6 mm.) (17.47 g., 0.1 mole) was added and the contents heated at 97°–100°, for 10 days. A considerable amount of sodium derivative as well as the chloro compound were present in the reaction mixture. Further 2.3 g. (0.1 mole) of sodium were added and the contents heated for another 5 days. The contents were filtered and distilled under reduced pressure. The major component in the high boiling fraction distilled at 115°–115.5°/0.55 mm. (distillation using an 18" spinning band column). Yield: 2.8 g. (10%) of purity at least 95–98%. (Calcd. for C₂₀H₃₂: C, 88.17; H, 11.82. Found: C, 88.36; H, 11.77). This compound has been assigned the structure 3-(*p'*-isopropylbenzyl)-*p*-menthane (IX) on the basis of evidence already discussed.

Oxidation of 3-(p'-isopropylbenzyl)-p-menthane: One gram of the title compound was oxidized with potassium permanganate. Terephthalic acid was identified in the oxidation products by infrared spectrometry.

Reaction of 2-Chloro-p-menthane with Sodium in Toluene: 2-Chloro-*p*-menthane was prepared by reaction of carvomenthol with PCl₅ in hexane. Carvomenthol was prepared by reduction of carvomenthone with LiAlH₄ according to standard procedures. Gas chromatography indicated the presence of two isomers. The component with lower retention time was isolated by distillation through a spinning band column; b.p. 71°–7°/2.3 mm. This fraction was used for further reactions. (Carvomenthone was obtained by hydrogenation of 1-carvone in absolute ethanol using platinum catalyst).

Reaction of 2-chloro-*p*-menthane with sodium and toluene and with *p*-cymene under conditions similar to those described for 3-chloro-*p*-menthane apparently did not occur in an analogous manner. The only product isolated was a low yield of a high boiling mixture containing three or four components. No aromatic nucleus was present in the products and the products were essentially saturated hydrocarbons.

*Reactions of 8-Bromo-p-menthene*¹⁷: (b.p. 68°–74°/0.1 mm.; yield: 64%). The lithium and Grignard reagents from 8-bromo-*p*-menthene were prepared by the reaction of lithium and magnesium respectively in ether. The reaction was initiated by addition of 3–5 drops of methyl iodide. Condensation of these reagents with menthone as well as with carvomenthone was attempted. There was no reaction at lower temperatures. At elevated temperatures (cyclohexane was added and contents heated to 70°–80°, allowing ether to escape) the organometallic reagent decomposed with the formation of very complex products but no condensation products were indicated.

Reduction of the Diepoxide of Dimer A with Lithium in Ethyl Amine: Diepoxide (0.5 g.) dissolved in 20 ml. ethyl amine was cooled to –20°. Metallic lithium (0.3 g.) was slowly added to the above mixture. The mixture was shaken during 5 hr at –20°. Then 1 g. NH₄Cl was added and the reaction mixture was poured on a basin to evaporate the ethylamine; water was added and the solution was neutralized with conc. HCl (pH ~ 7). It was then treated with five ml. (CH₃CO)₂O and two drops of dry pyridine and refluxed for 2 hr on the steam bath. The reaction product was then poured into ice and a semi-solid mass was obtained. This was passed through an acidic alumina column when a small amount

of crystalline solid was separated on chloroform-benzene elution. This was recrystallized from dilute alcohol; m.p. $92^{\circ}-4^{\circ}$.

Synthesis of 1-Methyl-2-hydroxy-2,4-diisopropyl Cyclohexane (X): All reagents and apparatus were perfectly dried. Magnesium turnings (9.6 g.), a small crystal of iodine and 140 ml. of dry ether were placed in a three-necked flask equipped with a condenser, stirrer and a separatory funnel. Isopropyl bromide (49.2 g.) diluted with 50 ml. of dry ether was placed in the separatory funnel fitted with a guard tube. The stirrer was started and 10-15 ml. of the bromide solution was added to the flask. The reaction started within a few minutes. It was cooled by tap water and the remainder of the bromide solution was then added dropwise. After complete addition of the bromide solution, the mixture was stirred further for 15 min; only a small residue of magnesium remained. The flask was then cooled by ice. Carvomenthone (61.6 g.) diluted with 50 ml. of dry ether was then placed in the separatory funnel and the solution was added dropwise. After complete addition, the mixture was refluxed on the steam bath for 2 hr. The flask was then cooled by ice. Ice/water followed by 6 (N) H_2SO_4 was added to decompose the Grignard complex after which the organic layer separated. The aqueous layer was then extracted with ether. The combined ether extracts, mixed; washed with $NaHSO_3$ solution (to remove iodine, added during starting of the reaction); washed with $NaHCO_3$, water dried and distilled at $80^{\circ}/1.2$ mm. (yield 10 g.). (Calc. for $C_{13}H_{26}O$: C, 78.77; H, 13.13; O, 8.08. Found: C, 78.53; H, 13.03; O, 8.44).

Preparation of 1-Methyl-2,4-diisopropyl-1-cyclohexane (XI): This compound was prepared by dehydration of compound X by iodine. X (5 g.) and iodine (250 mg.) were mixed and heated in an oil bath at $120^{\circ}-30^{\circ}$ for 1 hr and then distilled at $80^{\circ}/4.5$ mm.; yield, 3.5 g.

Preparation of Epoxide of Compound (XI): The procedure for this preparation was identical to that given in the preparation of the diepoxide of Dimer A. The crude epoxide was passed through an alumina column. The benzene eluted fraction gave the pure component. (Calc. for $C_{13}H_{24}O$: C, 79.59; H, 12.24; O, 8.17. Found: C, 80.06; H, 12.18; O, 7.76).

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